

DEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL
CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT MARCH 31, 2021
AMOUNT IN NAIRA

SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK (N)
1	ABIA	70,570,905,849.97
2	ADAMAWA	95,223,661,061.51
3	AKWA IBOM	232,204,284,318.65
4	ANAMBRA	59,710,637,126.27
5	BAUCHI	100,790,289,024.13
6	BAYELSA	142,936,287,958.14
7	BENUUE	128,252,738,662.85
8	BORNO	91,855,414,649.11
9	CROSS-RIVER	162,341,364,113.48
10	DELTA	213,782,129,604.56
11	EBONYI	43,790,839,758.40
12	EDO	81,750,262,718.83
13	EKITI	83,722,280,923.58
14	ENUGU	68,855,130,073.45
15	GOMBE	82,473,640,326.98
16	IMO	149,888,233,113.49
17	JIGAWA	31,572,060,237.67
18	KADUNA	68,754,361,083.75
19	KANO	119,427,638,899.46
20	KATSINA	58,339,331,273.92
21	KEBBI	55,096,954,426.87
22	KOGI	68,860,011,515.06
23	KWARA	63,243,935,109.34
24	LAGOS	507,377,449,198.76
25	NASARAWA	58,671,278,563.84
26	NIGER	62,327,267,332.33
27	OGUN	156,335,308,358.54
28	ONDO	72,598,126,601.96
29	OSUN	133,924,122,386.17
30	OYO	91,954,231,316.98
31	PLATEAU	134,223,134,679.17
32	RIVERS	266,936,225,793.65
33	SOKOTO	38,550,547,344.38
34	TARABA	100,004,214,754.69
35	YOBE	60,094,287,156.78
36	ZAMFARA	96,980,834,485.22
37	FCT	69,532,417,465.77
Total		4,122,951,837,267.70

Important Notes

1 This Domestic Debt Data Report is generated from the signed-off submissions received from the States and the FCT

2 Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty five (35) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamafara and the FCT as at March 31, 2021

3 Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 30, 2018